

BIM QUALITY ASSESSMENT FOR PROJECT MANAGEMENT

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Abstract

Building Information Modelling (BIM) has been modifying how building information is produced and communicated among the AEC stakeholders. For one side, BIM acts as a facilitator methodology; from the other side, it slows down the process by increasing the need of managing and controlling the information produced across project stages.

It is acknowledged that the model quality and reliability depends directly on how the data is structured beforehand. Therefore, the study focused on defining a framework for quality assurance of BIM models addressing the need to assess, manage, and maintain the information quality inside the authoring tool. The framework englobes three main parts: (1) preparation, (2) structuring the modelling process, and (3) application. A fluid workflow was proposed by addressing the requirements and quality acceptance criteria from the start of the project and integrating QA/QC tools into the modelling process. Yet, the field of quality checking is taken from the organisational perspective to provide a methodology that supports the team in generating quality project information and maintaining the model's quality across different projects. The proposed framework has the potential to be applied in any authoring software.

Among the contributions of the current work, the application of rules in the format of expression-based properties is highlighted. The study regarding its applicability for quality checks resulted in the generation of six categories of computable rules that feedback with COMPLIANT, NOT COMPLIANT or NOT APPLICABLE discrete values. This feature allowed the BIM objects to perform automated self-checking that can be easily integrated into the modelling stages. Furthermore, the rules feedbacks enables the generation of data for the quality assessment of the BIM model.

Dissertation:

<https://bimaplus.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/10/2021-TaianeBohrer-Dissertation.pdf>

Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/wGcgHTKZ-10>

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